

> **FUTURE FOCUS**

Practicing AI in Classrooms: Training, Gaming, Ethics, Earth, and Leadership

Written By:
Dr. Jane Spanich

In terms of Training, we need to teach students how to pick up AI. Students in high school are learning to grasp new technologies, books, websites, social media pages, and so on. Integrating an AI in classrooms setting is no longer a futuristic concept – it is a current necessity.

There should be an AI component in the handbooks and syllabi of each course as we continue down this technological trajectory. The AI platforms accessible to students are not the brains of their work, but the levers and guides. Students should not be using AI, generally speaking, when writing papers, submitting assignments to competitions, and problem solving with members of their classes.

The truth is that students and teachers have been using AI for years, the term AI is being more explored, fragmented, analyzed, and put into mainstream use. As long as there have been Robotics programs at schools, AI has been used. As long as gamifications, cell phones, websites have been utilized, AI has been part of the conversation.

Educators need to teach students a simple task, when to use AI and when not to use AI.

Navigating the Boundaries of AI in Classroom

There is a productive space for AI in classrooms environment when it comes to researching ideas, exploring real world conditions, preparing for presentations, obtaining public speaking tips, analyzing student data for academic progression and grasping success rates of particular career fields and practices.

AI can do incredible things when it comes to showing what classes students should be taking for a particular career path.

As long as the educator is clear to the students on when, where, how and why the students should be using AI, there is a place for AI in schools. Here it should be important that students, particularly in middle and high school, should understand the basics of AI Ethics, the difference between Good AI and Bad AI, and of course, AI Literacy.

I am currently the STREAM Director of a Roman Catholic school in Fort Lauderdale Florida. I recently published a book review on AI and the Image of God and presented on AI and Teaching Theology. Sometimes I let my students use AI, and sometimes I do not. My Phd is in Practical Theology and my Master's Degree is in Liberal Studies.

AI in classrooms: Role of Gaming and Simulation

Gamifications in schools have been utilizing AI for many years. I love games in the classroom or outside, especially on Fridays! There is a space for AI in classrooms when it comes to games. Google’s New AI plays Atari Games, Chess Games, Logic Games, and so on.

These AI connections can help elevate the strengths and skills of students. Furthermore, AI in classrooms is full of exciting new possibilities. AI games can come up with new strategies and challenges that make our students think more critically.

Even AI is able to gain points from particular games, this may help challenge the students to perform better. They are the ones with the brains after all.

When students practice certain skills such as logic games, problem solving, critical thinking, and public speaking, they have the ability to take their research to the next level.

Ethics, Bias, and Digital Citizenship

In STEM learning, anti-racism should be an important part of the conversation. Educators should reinforce the use of AI in classrooms that resembles and mimics good and ethical behavior, similar to the way in which teachers should present themselves in the classroom. They are role models for the students!

Perhaps an English teacher can demonstrate the ways in which the protagonist of the story, using AI in classrooms, can be mimicked or mirrored in the daily lives of students.

Perhaps a Theology teacher can have AI in classrooms (Chat GPT or Magiserium AI) list out the ways in which acts of discipleship can impact the daily lives of students in terms of happiness, virtue, value and human dignity. There are people behind the scenes with every algorithm that is coded with AI.

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That said, what we say to AI and how students act with AI matters.

It is important for students to understand that racist bots are failed AI attempts. It is important for them to continue to ask questions – isn't that what education is all about for the most part? Thankfully, companies, for the most part, are honest when their AI bots take a wrong turn. There is an ethical line in the macro conversation of AI that can be explored with our students in order to make a peaceful and civilized society. In addition, we need to demonstrate that robotics and AI actually have pretty good listening skills. Can students learn from this in terms of listening skills?

ECO-AI: Using Technology for the Planet

AI is doing some incredible work when it comes to the environment. AI is fighting wildlife poaching, creating conversations with agriculture and medical communities, battling unhealthy air conditions, as well as deforestation help to name a few.

For students who are interested in being part of this conversation, which many of them are, educators need to demonstrate the ways in which AI is rising to meet the needs of environmentalists, scientists, farmers, astronomers, artists, geneticists, and so on. AI will impact every career in the near future (if it hasn't already).

Here it is important to note the Gen Z and Millennials are more concerned with climate change conversations than older generations (Pew Research, 2021). The time is now to have the conversations in the classroom – with students, parents, educational leaders on their approaches to AI education and AI in classrooms.

AI in Classroom: Conclusion

The advancement of AI, generally speaking, is not something that I am necessarily afraid of. What concerns me is if educators, philosophers, theologians, ethicists, ethnographers, to name a few, are not part of the conversation.

Finally, I want to note that I did not use AI when writing this article.

By bringing AI in classroom discussions to the forefront, we ensure that the next generation uses these tools to build a more advanced, ethical, and sustainable world.

Reference:

1. Wang, S., Wang, F., Zhu, Z., Wang, J., Tran, T., & Du, Z. (2024). Artificial intelligence in education: A systematic literature review. *Expert Systems With Applications*, 252, 124167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eswa.2024.124167>
2. Nadeem, R., & Nadeem, R. (2025, April 24). Gen Z, millennials stand out for climate change activism, social media engagement with issue. *Pew Research Center*. <https://www.pewresearch.org/science/2021/05/26/gen-z-millennials-stand-out-for-climate-change-activism-social-media-engagement-with-issue/>

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